

DASH Conference Meeting Summary (from GPT-4)

Generated by Shawn Polson

Monday "Data"

Session 0: Opening Plenary talks

Speakers: Laura Hayes, Alisdair Davey, Baptiste Cecconi

- The overarching theme revolved around efficiently managing and accessing the vast amount of heliophysics data available.
- Laura Hayes emphasized the need for meaningful crosswalks between directories/archives/catalogues and highlighted the ongoing challenges like data discovery, data source disparity, and interdisciplinary standards.
- Alisdair Davey questioned mechanisms for adding data discoveries and discussed issues such as data heterogeneity and transitioning from IDL to Python.
- Baptiste Cecconi discussed the distinction between 'accessible' and 'usable' data, suggesting that tracking events requires data linked by phenomena. He also highlighted the potential of Machine Learning in heliophysics.

Notable points:

1. **Centralized Directory:** There's a call for a centralized directory or easily navigable portal for all heliophysics data, including software documentation.
2. **Future Vision:** A suggestion for a "helioGPT" where one can use natural language processing to find and filter relevant observations in heliophysics.
3. **Community Collaboration:** Challenges such as siloed funding and the need for improved interoperability were discussed.

Session 1: Cloud Computing for Heliophysics

Highlights:

- **Heliocloud:** An initiative to measure the scientific impact of cloud computing in Heliophysics, aiming to integrate with DOI minting systems.
- **Data Transfer and Storage:** Discussions around AWS tools like s3, Elastic File System, and Elastic Block Storage to speed up data transfer and processing.
- **Importance of Cloud:** Need to highlight real-world impacts of cloud computing on science beyond mere citations.

Session 2: Modern Data Pipeline Strategies

Highlights:

- **Globus as a Tool:** Globus was extensively discussed for its role in connecting infrastructure to the science it enables.
- **Community Involvement:** Emphasis on the community's role in extending and improving data pipelines.
- **Data Versioning:** The importance of version control for datasets was underscored, with references to established protocols and practices.

Session 3: Data Access Interfaces and Services

Highlights:

- **FAIR Principles:** Mark Parsons discussed the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and emphasized the importance of understanding how things relate.
- **HAPI:** Several discussions around the Heliophysics API (HAPI) and its role in providing quick data access, while noting its current limitations.
- **User Engagement:** Different strategies to engage with users and gather feedback were highlighted, including annual reviews, workshops, and informal interest groups.
- **Data Citing:** The challenge of citing dynamic data was raised, with suggestions like versioning and timestamping every data point.

Key Takeaways:

1. **Interoperability is Key:** Many discussions centered around the need for better interoperability between data sources, cloud systems, and computing tools.

2. **Centralized Data Directory:** There's a strong desire within the community for a centralized or easily navigable portal for all heliophysics data.
3. **Engaging the Community:** There's a need for improved community collaboration, both in terms of feedback mechanisms and in terms of pooling resources to address common challenges.
4. **Embracing Modern Tools:** Tools like Globus, HAPI, and cloud platforms are being embraced, but with a recognition that more needs to be done to maximize their potential.

Day one of the inaugural DASH workshop emphasized the need to efficiently harness the vast amount of data available in the heliophysics domain. The discussions illuminated challenges and presented pathways for streamlined data access, efficient computing, and enhanced community collaboration. As the field continues to grow, the insights from this conference will undoubtedly guide future endeavors.

Tuesday "Analysis"

Session 4: Optimizing ML SWx Modeling and Forecasting through Improved Data Sets and Metrics

Speakers: Evangelos Paouris, Julie Vievering, Juan Camilo Buitrago-Casas

Highlights:

- The session included 10 lightning talks (each 5 minutes) and a 30-minute discussion.
- Paul Wright introduced a project called ARCAFF that deals with Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting, shared via the website arcaff.eu and its [GitHub repository](#).
- Tools like MLFlow, MLOps, and Weights & Biases were mentioned for ensuring documentation and reproducibility.
- Discussion on benchmark datasets for CMEs was held, emphasizing the need for a community effort and standardization. Paul Wright suggested the creation of a website for comparing ML tasks, paper citations, dataset and model descriptions, and metrics.

Session 5: Computational notebooks in heliophysics

Speakers: Shawn Polson, Jack Wang, Eric Grimes, Jan Gieseler, Min-Yang Chou

Highlights:

- The session included several talks, followed by a discussion on Miro board.
- James Mason pointed attendees to helioml.org for chapters on heliophysics and computational methods.
- Shawn Polson discussed "Executable papers" and introduced one such paper.
- A significant part of the discussion revolved around the benefits of executable papers (EPs). EPs enhance reproducibility by integrating code, data, and dependencies directly into the research paper.

Session 6: Interoperability between Python Packages (PyHC)

Speakers: Rebecca Ringuette, Will Barnes, Nabil Freij, Stuart Mumford

Highlights:

- Emphasis was laid on the importance of software testing and community contributions.
- The challenges faced by many packages, including becoming "vaporware" and small bus factor, were discussed.
- Recommendations like "Program to an interface, not an implementation" were shared.

Unconference Sessions:

1. Broadening participation in open-source projects:
 - The need for research software engineering skills in open-source development was stressed.
 - Various ways to attract core contributors were discussed, including GitHub's "hacktoberfest".
 - The significance of having psychological safety in communities and the importance of contribution guides were highlighted.

2. Event List Sharing (is caring):

- Discussions centered around how event lists are vital for various heliophysics applications and research. Emphasis was on standards, metadata, and community adoption of common definitions.
- A call for collaboration and a unified approach was evident, with mentions of HELIONAUTS.org as a potential platform.

3. What's Out There?

- Focused on ideas for collecting links to open-source helio-related tools, codes, databases, and event lists.
- Issues with current tools were discussed, such as outdated resources and the lack of uniform terminology in the field.
- The need for "smart" tools and open science policies was evident. Initiatives like NASA's "Open Science for Science Missions" were presented as solutions to current challenges.

Key Takeaways:

- There's a growing interest in optimizing data and models for ML in SWx forecasting.
- The community sees immense value in executable research articles for increasing the reproducibility of scientific findings.
- Interoperability between Python packages remains a concern, with an emphasis on community-driven standards and contributions.
- Open-source projects require a broadened participation, with a focus on teaching research software engineering skills.
- Event lists are crucial but need standards, uniformity, and collaboration.
- The community needs a consolidated resource hub for heliophysics tools, codes, and databases. Open science policies and unified platforms can address current challenges.

Day two of the inaugural DASH workshop delved deeper into the intricacies of data analysis, focusing on optimization, reproducibility, and collaboration. The day kicked off with an exploration into machine learning and its best practices, transitioning into the significance of computational notebooks and "Executable papers" in enhancing research reproducibility. Further discussions centered on the importance of interoperability between Python packages, with a clear emphasis on community-driven standards. The unconference sessions highlighted the human side of open-source

projects, emphasizing psychological safety, broader participation, and the pivotal role of event lists in heliophysics. The day culminated with a call for a centralized resource repository for tools and codes, embodying the collective vision of the community for holistic progress in heliophysics research.

Wednesday "Software"

Session 7: Moving to all open-source in Heliophysics

Summary: This breakout session started with a brief introduction about the format, followed by five main talks. The topics revolved around open development and open-source release in Heliophysics, with discussions on challenges and successes in transitioning to open source. Key points include:

- SWxSOC's shift from old data processing pipelines to an open-source model was highlighted by Damian Barrous-Dume.
- C. Bard introduced MARBLE, emphasizing the importance of making an open-source code that is user-friendly, functional, and adaptable.
- Chiu Wiegand shared insights from the NASA's CCMC, addressing the procedural intricacies of making code public within the space agency.
- Rebecca Ringuette, through Brian Thomas, stressed the importance of open science, recommending the use of permissive licenses.
- Josh Steele shared APL's journey towards embracing open science, addressing the challenges and emphasizing community involvement.

Takeaways:

1. Open sourcing in Heliophysics faces challenges like Intellectual Property issues and the balancing act between publication needs and open sharing.
2. An actionable recommendation is the proposal to add a PyHC FAQ page to address community questions.
3. An impending NASA funding opportunity, specifically for Python, will be available soon.

Session 8: Advancing Data Portals for Open Heliophysics Research

Summary: This breakout session revolved around how Heliophysics data, metadata, and tools can be made accessible through intuitive user interfaces. Several data portals and tools were showcased:

- Robert Candey introduced three data portals (CDAWeb, HDP, SDE) based on different metadata standards.
- Eric Donovan discussed the ASI All Sky Imager network, emphasizing the importance of metadata to filter out non-useful data.
- Eelco Dornboos highlighted the Space Weather Timeline Viewer that collates various data essential for space weather monitoring.
- Giuseppe Romeo presented the RBSP science gateway, a hub to correlate data from different instruments.
- Masha Kuznetsova discussed the offerings of CCMC.
- Lutz Rastaetter showcased the CAMEL tool, while Ryan McGranaghan introduced Helio-KNOW.

Takeaways:

1. Review of tools and platforms like CDAWeb, HDPE, CCMC, RSPB, SwarmX, AuroraX, KNMI space weather timeline viewer, and Helio-NOW.
2. There's a need for standardizing metadata and APIs, as evidenced by the widespread use of SPASE.
3. The value of community feedback was emphasized, along with mechanisms to gather it.
4. HAPI servers and SPASE are instrumental in integrating disparate data sources.
5. Presentation by Laura Hayes highlighted the challenges of interdisciplinary research and emphasized the creation of a unified reader, standardized event databases, and a public heliophysics documentation system.

Session 9: Methods and Software Tools for Forward Synthesis and Inverting Plasma and Magnetic Information in the Solar Corona

Summary: This breakout session began with Gabe Dima setting the scene about the challenges posed by the integrated nature of the solar corona. The lightning talks

showcased various tools and methods developed for modeling, analyzing, and visualizing solar corona data:

- Gelu Nita and Sarah Gibson introduced GX-Simulator and FORWARD respectively, both for coronal modeling.
- Mike Galloy announced the relaunch of UCoMP in Spring '24.
- Several other tools like ScatpolPy, CLEDB, SunRF, Solar-MACH, and FAIR were presented.

Takeaways:

1. The community discussed mechanisms for code discovery and avoiding duplicate efforts. Drawing from the computer science community, the use of forks and pull-requests was highlighted.
2. The importance of incorporating reproducibility criteria in research was stressed, with an emphasis on community self-organization.
3. The use of Jupyter notebooks was highlighted as a way to ensure user engagement and value addition.

Day three of the DASH Conference showcased the progressive steps the Heliophysics community is taking towards open-source and collaborative research. The discussions emphasized the importance of community engagement, feedback, and the integration of advanced tools for better research outcomes. The actionable takeaways provided a roadmap for immediate next steps and improvements in the field.

Major Takeaways from DASH:

- Discussion on the standardization of event lists and the need for flexibility.
- Emphasis on the importance of standards bodies.
- A need to systematize resources to ensure they are easily accessible to newcomers.
- The challenge of having disparate datasets and tools spread across multiple heliophysics platforms.
- Importance of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus for vocabulary.
- Encouragement to increase participation in open source projects.
- Announcement: PyHC to host a summer school in May 2024.
- Discussions on the successful model of SunPy's contributor community.

- The crucial role of connection and community in attracting contributors.
- Debates on the potential risks of open source and the challenges of recognition and citation in open science.
- Emphasis on the ethical considerations of AI and the balance of applied versus basic research.
- Launch of SciX by ADS in December and its role as a repository.
- The presence and importance of other programming languages besides Python.
- Discussion on the necessity and benefits of open science.

Suggestions for Next Year's DASH

- Implement a dedicated Slack channel for improved interaction between both virtual and in-person attendees.
- Propose a unique thread for questions/comments for each session.
- Advocate for longer presentation durations by reducing the number of speakers.
- Allow speakers to use their personal computers for the convenience of accessing their notes.
- Encourage more hands-on demonstrations over traditional presentations.
- Increase the number of unconference sessions.
- Consider providing attendees with event T-shirts.
- Present QR codes alongside short links.
- Offer a comprehensive agenda complete with speaker details, talk titles, etc.
- Allow the event schedule to remain flexible until abstract submissions are completed.

Conclusion

Overall, the DASH Conference provided a pivotal platform, drawing together heliophysics professionals from diverse areas of expertise. Over the course of the sessions, it became evident that the community is ardently focused on enhancing interoperability, optimizing data utilization for machine learning, and promoting open science through comprehensive software and data strategies. Central themes, such as the importance of community collaboration, the potential of modern tools, and the urgency for standardization, resonated throughout the discussions. Additionally, the

push towards a more open-source environment signaled a collective aspiration to make heliophysics research more inclusive, reproducible, and impactful. The spirited debates, combined with actionable insights, ensure that the DASH conference's reverberations will be felt in the field for years to come, catalyzing transformative shifts in how heliophysics research is conducted and disseminated.